

Research Article

Sieve Analysis for the Determination of the Liberation Size of Galena at Zurak, Wase
L. G. A., Plateau State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Comminution was done on galena collected from Zurak for the determination of liberation size and enrichment of valuable particles size from the galena ore matrix using a laboratory ball mill. The product was sieved using a sieve shaker which gave various sizes of +300, -300+250, -200+150, -150+100 and -100+75 μ m. A cumulative of optimum weight percent retained and passed were calculated and plotted against a graph of particle sizes. The elemental percent compositions of the minerals in the respective sieve sizes were examined with the use of Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS). The AAS result agrees with the graphical result in which the optimum liberation particle size of between -100 +75 μ m yielded 55.53 and 47.47% weights retained and passed respectively and an elemental recovery of a high concentration of zinc, lead and iron at 12.05, 18.09 and 10.03% in that order. Wills (2007) established that the optimum particle size of galena ore liberated in order to give maximum concentration or recovery of valuable minerals should be between +200 and -75 μ m with a weight percent (wt %) retaining and passing as 60 and 40 respectively. Therefore, the determined results are much closed to the findings by Wills (2007) and hence Zurak galena can be optimally liberated and zinc, lead and iron be recovered at higher concentrations.

Keywords: Liberation, Sieve analysis, Elemental analysis, Particle size, Comminution

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Introduction

As a result of most minerals being finely disseminated and intimately associated with the gangue, they must be first of all be 'liberated' or 'unlocked' before separation can be done. It is achieved by a process called comminution (crushing and grinding) in which the particle size of the ore is progressively reduced until the clean particles of mineral can be separated. Comminution in its earliest stages is carried out in order to make the freshly excavated material easier to handle by scrapers, conveyors, and ore carriers and in the case of quarry products to produce material of controlled particle size (Wills and Napier-Munn, 2007; Kinnarid, 2004 and Yan and Gupta, 2006).

Comminution is employed in the mineral processing plant to primarily and substantially release the mineral from the gangue as separate particles. Crushing is the first stage in a mechanical comminution process with the main objective to liberate or reduce boulder ore sizes to smaller ones thereby freeing valuable minerals from the associated gangue. Crushing is done by the compression of the ore against rigidly constrained motion path. This precedes grinding which is accomplished by abrasion and impact of the ore either dry or wet by the free motion of unconnected media such as rods, balls or pebbles (Wills and Atkinson, 2003).

When the comminution process is completed, the subsequent operations in mineral processing are taken over by separation and concentration. Regardless of the method(s) used, the aim is always the same - to take a natural aggregate of minerals (an ore) and separate it into two or more mineral products. In general, the products of separation are the concentrate which contains the valuable minerals and the tailings which consists basically materials of little or no value (Lynch and Morrell, 2002). It must be noted that minerals that have been liberated either by grinding or by chemical means must be sized or classified before their separation from each other because the efficiencies of most separation methods are enhanced when closely sized fractions are utilized (Flavel, 2008). The feature of all separation processes is that they are usually imperfect, that is, some of the worthless materials contaminate the concentrate to some extent, and some of the valuables in small amounts are always present in the tailings (Levin, 2009). Hence, the liberation must be at optimum particle size.

Sieving comes after the comminution process and is among the oldest methods of size analysis which is achieved by passing a particular weight of sample material successively through finer sieves and weighing the quantity obtained on each sieve to calculate the percentage weight in each size fraction. Sieving is carried out with wet or dry materials

and the sieves are usually agitated to expose all the particles to the openings (Putman, 2003).

Djordjevic *et al.* (2004) said when sieving is done to irregularly shaped particles, it becomes difficult as a result of a particle having a size close to that of the nominal aperture of the test sieve and it may pass only when presented in a favourable position. Schuhmann, (2000) showed that prolonged sieving makes the bigger apertures to experience unnecessary sizeable effect on the sieve analysis when there is unavoidably a difference in the size of sieve apertures due to inconsistencies of weaving. With time, most particles small enough may find their way through some of those few holes.

Test sieving is the most widely utilized method for particle size analysis. It covers a very wide range of particle sizes which becomes one of most industrial importance. Test sieving is a common method of size analysis that particles finer than about 75 μ m are always referred to as being in the sub-sieverange, though modern sieving techniques permits sizing to be carried out to about 5 μ m. Different types of sieve aperture ranges are currently used, the most common are the German Standard, DIN 4188; ASTM standard, E11; the American Tyler series; the French series, AFNOR; and the British Standard, B S 1796. (Djordjevic, 2005).

The removal of some specific valuable minerals from their naturally occurring ores is term as 'ore dressing', or 'mineral beneficiation'. There is the need for the transformation by beneficiation of natural metalliferous ore produced by mining operation to pure metal. It is very necessary to develop and bring about sustainable effective and good economic process of separation as the aim of mineral concentration operations is to maximally liberate the marketable values from the gangue with negligible loss of the valuables in tailings. The concentrate of the valuable minerals from the gangue involves exploitation in the mineral operation of the differences in the mineral properties of the ore after effective comminution (Wills, 2006).

Maurin and Benkhelil (2000) gave the chemical composition of galena to include Pb, Zn, Sb, Ag, Cu, Ca, Bi, Fe, As, Si and Mo. Lead (Pb) and zinc (Zn) having 80.6% and 10.4% respectively. Galena is brittle with hardness and specific gravity of 2 - 3 and 7.4 - 7.6 in that order, having poor electrical conductivity and good rectifying properties (Adepoju *et al.*, 2000).

Galena is the most important ore of lead, depending on the presence of associated minerals; it can be a good source of sulphur, silver, zinc etc (InoueandOkaya, 2005)

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Galena is hydrothermally associated with sphalerite in its process. The sphalerite has impurities such as iron (Fe), sulphur (S), pyrrhotite (FeS) and chalcopyrite (CuFeS₂) (Rose and Butt 2009). Wills (2006) revealed that the liberation or release of the ore from the associated gangue mineral must be at the coarsest possible particle size, which if underground, much more reagents will be used to further concentrate the mineral or if over ground, the mineral particles may be taken as slime and more energy be used. If such an aim is achieved, then not only is energy saved by the reduction of the amount of fines produced, but any subsequent separation stages become easier and cheaper to operate.

Zurak is located at the extreme eastern part of Wase Local Government Area of Plateau State within the Latitude and Longitude of 9° 15' N and 32" E. It is approximately 300m above the sea level. Prior to colonial era, galena was locally worked on by the aborigines on a small scale which they used for adornment or as cosmetics and was abandoned before 1931 (Adegoke *et al.*, 2006). The Colonial administration took interest in the lead, zinc and silver in Zurak Mines as it was called in 1931 and commenced extraction which extended to a depth of about 80 meters and they too left in 1937 as a result of fall in metal prices, since there was unavailability of information on the chemical analysis of the deposit (FMMSD, 2010).

This research study seeks to establish the particle size of galena at which the various grains in the ore will be freed of each other, thus setting the stage for particle size analysis and percent composition of minerals in the various particle sizes for effective and efficient separation process as well as beneficiating the ore by appropriate method of concentration.

The aim of this work is to:

- (i) Determine the liberation size range of the galena at Zurak without necessarily over or under-grinding the material.
- (ii) Help avoid the unnecessary consumption of reagents, energy and time if the galena is either underground or over-ground.
- (iii) Determine the percent composition of the minerals of interest (zinc, lead and iron) in the various particle sizes therein and make comparison with the graphical result.

Methodology

In order to have a true fraction representation of galena from the bulk, sampling was done at the Zurak Mines where sample was collected from sixteen different points at depths of 3 to 4 meters each within the study area of 2km². The samples collected in lumps were broken manually with sledge hammer to provide a required size acceptable to laboratory jaw crusher. The conning and quartering was carried out to give a representative sample.

The laboratory jaw crusher was used to reduce the 50 to +100mm size of the sample brought from the site. This crushed material was put into a laboratory ball mill where it was ground to appreciable particle sizes for 10 minutes. The sieves were properly cleaned with sieve brush and then arranged onto the sieve shaker using the Taylor sieve formula ($\sqrt{2}$) (Craig and Vaughan, 2001).

$$\text{Sieve number one} = \frac{\text{Sieve number two}}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{Sieve number two} = \frac{\text{Sieve number three}}{\sqrt{2}} \text{ e. t. c.}$$

Continuous division of the answer by $\sqrt{2}$ gives the sequence of the sieve arrangement. The sieves were arranged from 300 to 75 μ m with the coarsest sieve on the top and the finest at the bottom. A tight fitting pan was placed at the bottom of the last sieve to receive the final undersize. A sample of 200g was fed onto the coarsest sieve and covered with a lid to prevent escape of the sample. Electric power was put on and the sieve shaker was then operated which continuously moved the material vertically up and down for 15 minutes. During the shaking, the undersize material fell through successive sieves until it was retained on a sieve having apertures which were slightly smaller than the diameter of the particles. After a successful operation each size fraction retained on each sieve was collected, weighed and recorded. A graph of percent retained and percent passed was plotted against the sieve size.

Analysis of Elemental Percent Composition

A potential difference was applied between the anode and the cathode of the AAS which led to the ionization of some gas atoms of the sample placed in it. These gaseous ions bombarded the cathode and ejected metal atoms from the cathode in a process called sputtering. Some sputtered atoms were in excited states and emitted radiation characteristic of the metal as they fell back to the ground state.

The shape of the cathode which is hollow cylindrical concentrated the emitted radiation into a beam which passed through a quartz window all the way to the vaporized sample. Since atoms of different elements absorb characteristic wavelengths of light. The analysis of a sample to see if it contains a particular element means using light from that element. For example with lead, a lamp containing lead emits light from excited lead atoms that produce the right mix of wavelengths to be absorbed by any lead atoms from the sample. A beam of the electromagnetic radiation emitted from excited lead atoms was passed through the vaporized sample. Some of the radiation was absorbed by the lead atoms in the sample. The greater the number of atoms there is in the vapour, the more radiation is absorbed.

The role of the atom cell was to primarily dissolve a liquid sample and then the solid particles were vaporized into their free gaseous ground state form. In this form atoms were available to absorb radiation emitted from the light source and thus generated a measurable signal proportional to concentration.

The light selected by the monochromator was directed onto a detector that is typically a photomultiplier tube whose function is to convert the light signal into an electrical signal proportional to the light intensity. The processing of electrical signal was fulfilled by a signal amplifier. The signal displayed spectrum from the sample having the concentration of the elements in each of the particle size samples and the result saved and printed (Table 1.0).

Results and Discussion

Figure 1.0 shows that the optimum weight percent retained and weight percent passed are 55.53 and 47.47% corresponding with sieve size between -100 and +75 μ m. This means that Zurak galena at particle sizes from -100 to +75 μ m can give the weight percent of 55.53% and 47.47% retaining and passing respectively. According to Wills (2006) this is within a good particle size that liberates or exposes substantial amount of lead and zinc for concentration without so much application of energy and reagents.

Fig. 1.0: Cumulative Retained – Passed and Particle Size Graph

Table 1.0: Elemental Composition of Zurak Galena by AAS

Aperture size (µm)	Si (%)	Ca (%)	Mn (%)	Fe (%)	Ni (%)	Cu (%)	Zn (%)	Ag (%)	Bi (%)	Pb (%)
+300	6.76	1.12	0.06	9.8	1.07	0.19	5.00	0.09	1.05	8.70
-300+200	5.96	1.19	1.09	5.11	1.08	0.09	3.98	0.01	0.52	13.24
-200+150	13.10	0.03	1.02	0.43	0.09	0.30	6.50	1.00	3.12	8.77
-150+100	3.68	0.05	0.10	-	1.00	0.02	9.80	-	1.20	8.99
-100+75	5.09	0.50	0.01	10.0	1.00	-	12.05	2.50	3.02	18.09

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Table 1.0 is the elemental analysis which was conducted on all the five sieve sizes. This shows that at particle size +300µm the minerals of interest, zinc and lead were still embedded in the gangue hence giving lower percentages of 5% and 8.7% respectively. At between -300 and +200µm particle sizes, lead was better liberated and zinc wasn't dissociated well. Between -200 and +150µm and -150 and +100µm particle sizes of both zinc and lead were not appreciably liberated, probably due to coarse nature of the material. In all the particle sizes above, higher percentage of silica is observed in sieve sizes of -200 to +150µm with a moderate unlocking of zinc and lead. Zinc and lead are highly exposed or liberated at particle sizes between -100 and +75µm with lower amounts of silica and silver and a good amount of iron.

Conclusion

The AAS results confirmed the result in Figure 1.0 that the optimal liberation particle size can be achieved using the sieve sizes between -100 and +75 μ m which yielded 55.53% retained and 47.47% passed and percent compositions of iron, zinc and lead as 10.03, 12.05 and 18.09% respectively in which the Zurak iron, zinc and lead can be recovered from galena ore to achieve high concentration.

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